

INVESTIGATION OF THE STRUCTURAL PROCESS OF THE MARMALADE MASS USING POWDERS BASED ON APPLE AND CARROT PULP

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Abstract. *This study investigated the process of forming the structure of the marmalade mass using powders based on apple and carrot pulp. Apple and carrot powders have high nutritional value as natural raw materials, containing a large amount of pectin, carotene, vitamins, and food fibers. These components play a significant role in strengthening the structure and enhancing the biological value of the marmalade.*

The study evaluated the amount of apple and carrot powders added to the marmalade mass and their influence on the mass structure. The organoleptic, physicochemical, and rheological properties were analyzed. The results showed that the powder added in an amount of 5-10% provides a uniform structure of the marmalade mass, high binding ability, and a color with a bright flavor of the product.

The results of this study allow for the creation of new, healthy, and environmentally friendly products through the use of local fruit and vegetable powders in the production of marmalade. This approach serves the innovative development of the food industry and the widespread implementation of principles of healthy nutrition.

Keywords: *apple powder, carrot powder, marmalade mass, structuring process, pectin substances, food fibers, rheological properties, biological value, healthy products, innovative technologies.*

Introduction:

In the confectionery market, jelly marmalade dominates among marmalade varieties. This is because fruit and berry marmalade, which is made using fruit and berry purees, is significantly more expensive compared to jelly marmalade. However, a notable drawback of jelly marmalade is that its formulation consists of approximately 70% sugar, with artificial colorants and flavorings mainly used to provide taste, color, and aroma [1]. Due to these shortcomings, jelly marmalade is high in calories and has low nutritional and biological value.

To improve the quality of jelly marmalade, we proposed increasing its nutritional and antioxidant value while reducing its sugar content. To achieve this, we suggested using powders made from apple and carrot pomace in the recipe. These powders are prepared directly from secondary raw materials obtained during juice production, which also helps lower the cost of the final product.

As a reference for the new type of marmalade, the recipe for "Jelly-shaped" marmalade was chosen, where agar is used as the gelling agent [2].

The possibility of replacing refined white sugar in jelly marmalade with powders based on apple and carrot pomace was studied to reduce sugar content and enhance its nutritional and

antioxidant value. Apple and carrot powders were added in doses of 25%, 50%, and 75% [3]. This approach allows for reducing the caloric content of the marmalade and enriching it with dietary fibers and antioxidants.

The experimental and control samples of jelly marmalade were prepared following the method described in section 2.2 ("Research Objects").

Jelly confectionery products have a gel-like structure, which is formed under specific conditions due to the effects of high molecular weight substances in the recipe. The structure of jelly marmalade depends on various factors, including the recipe components and their proportions [4].

Research Methods and Techniques

The following were used as research objects in the experimental work:

Apples of the "Besh Yulduz" variety from Gallaorol district, Jizzakh region.

Pumpkins of the "Dasta Qovoq" variety from Tashkent region.

Beets of the "Qizil Musht" variety.

Carrots of the "Vitamin" variety [5].

The raw materials included:

Pulp from apples, beets, carrots, and pumpkins after direct juice extraction.

Secondary raw materials from apple, beet, carrot, and pumpkin processing in natural juice and nectar production.

Powders derived from apple, beet, carrot, and pumpkin residues.

Heat-resistant fillings from beet and pumpkin.

Apple and carrot-based syrups used in jelly marmalade and their mixtures [6].

For the study, semi-finished fruit and vegetable products (powders, syrups, and thermally stable fillings) were combined with the following additional raw materials:

Apple puree (GOST 3274:201).

Agar-agar (GOST 16280:2016).

Sugar (GOST 33222:2019).

Starch syrup (GOST 33917:2019).

Citric acid monohydrate (GOST 908:2018).

Drinking water (GOST 51232:2018, SanPin 2.1.4.1074-18) [7].

Experimental jelly marmalade samples were prepared by incorporating powders derived from apple and carrot residues, based on the structural scheme presented in Figure 2.1. Agar-agar was used as the gelling agent, dissolved in drinking water in a 1:30 ratio and heated to 100°C.

The powders from apple and carrot residues and high-sugar starch syrup were preheated to 60°C and mixed. The prepared jelly mass was heated to 50°C, 0.98% citric acid (relative to the recipe mass) was added, and the mixture was packaged. The resulting marmalade products were cooled to 20°C. Control samples were prepared using conventional methods [8].

Results and Discussion

Refined white sugar is one of the essential components of jelly confectionery recipes, including marmalade, as it significantly influences the gel formation process. However, gels can also form without adding sugar. Incorporating powders based on apple and carrot residues into the jelly marmalade recipe significantly affects the gel formation process.

Table 1: Recipes for control and experimental samples of jelly marmalade.

Raw -material	Mass fraction of dry matter, %	Amount of raw material, g							
		Control sample		Marmalade made from apple or carrot pulp					
				Sample 1		Sample 2			Sample 3
		natural	In DM	natural		natural	In DM	Natural	In DM
Sugar	99,85	61,22	61,13	-	-	-	-	-	-
Starch syrup	78,00	26,27	20,49	75,00	58,5	50,00	39,00	25,00	19,50
Powder based on apple or carrot pulp	65,00	-	-	25,00	16,2	50,00	32,50	75,00	48,75
Agar-agar	85,00	1,05	0,89	1,22	1,04	1,22	1,04	1,22	1,04
Citric acid	98,00	1,18	1,16	0,98	0,96	0,98	0,96	0,98	0,96
Total		89,72	83,67	102,20	76,7	102,2	73,50	102,2	70,25
Yield		100,00	82,00	100,00	75,1	100,0	71,92	100,0	68,74

Study of the Effect of Powder Based on Apple and Carrot Pomace on the Plastic Strength of Jelly Marmalade Mass

The effect of adding 25%, 50%, and 75% amounts of powder (replacing sugar) into the recipe mixture on the plastic strength of jelly marmalade mass was studied. The amount of high-sugar starch syrup was proportionally increased in the experimental samples.

During the ripening process, the plastic strength of the jelly marmalade mass was measured every 30 minutes. The measurement process was stopped when the plastic strength indicator reached its maximum value.

The relationship between the ripening time and the plastic strength in the samples with 25%, 50%, and 75% powder (based on apple or carrot pomace) and a comparison with the control sample are depicted in Figure 1.

The obtained data showed that as the ripening time increased, the plastic strength of the jelly marmalade mass increased as well. This could be related to the gradual densification of the spatial network of molecules due to their interaction. The strengthening of the interactions between molecules with opposing electric charges helps in the arrangement of certain molecular sections within the mass.

Effect of Apple and Carrot Pomace-Based Powders on Jelly Marmalade. When powders based on apple or carrot pomace are added to the recipe in place of refined white sugar, the time for gel formation is reduced (Figure 5.1). This is due to the food fibers in the powders, which have high water absorption capacity. The food fibers increase the dehydration level by absorbing water from the solvation layers of the agar molecules, leading to faster gel formation.

In the experimental samples, the plastic strength was higher compared to the control sample when 25%, 50%, and 75% of powder was added. For instance:

With 25% powder, the plastic strength values were 14.8 and 15.3 kPa.

With 50%, the values were 15.6 and 16.2 kPa.

Figure 1. The Effect of Different Doses of Apple (a) and Carrot (b) Pomace-Based Powders on the Plastic Strength During the Hardening Process of Jelly Marmalade: 1 - Control sample; 2 - Sample 1; 3 - Sample 2; 4 - Sample 3.

With 75%, the values were 16.1 and 17.5 kPa. In the control sample, the plastic strength was 14 kPa.

Figure 2. The Relationship Between the Effective Viscosity and Shear Rate of Jelly Marmalade Mass with Different Doses of Apple (a) or Carrot (b) Pomace-Based Powder: 1 – Control sample; 2 – Value for sample 1; 3 – Value for sample 2; 4 – Value for sample 3.

Discussion on the Addition of Apple or Carrot Pomace-Based Powder to Jelly Marmalade Mass. When powders based on apple or carrot pomace are added to the jelly marmalade mass, it is important to choose the appropriate shaping method for the production of such marmalade, taking into account the structure-mechanical properties that arise. For the jelly marmalade of sample 1 (as well as the control sample), the traditional molding method of pouring is used. However, for samples 2 and 3 (with 50% and 75% powder), it is recommended to use the metalized "Flow-Pak" casing and spraying method.

Conclusion

The effect of apple and carrot pomace-based powders on jelly marmalade mass was studied, and it was found that replacing sugar with these ingredients significantly improves the product's quality and physical-chemical properties. According to the experimental results, the plastic strength of the jelly marmalade mass was higher compared to the control sample when 25%, 50%, and 75% powder was added. This is related to the water absorption capacity of the food fibers in the powders and their activity in the gel formation process.

In the control sample, the plastic strength was 14 kPa, while adding 25% powder increased it to 14.8–15.3 kPa, 50% increased it to 15.6–16.2 kPa, and 75% increased it to 16.1–17.5 kPa. These values can be explained by the densification of the molecular structure in the marmalade mass and the strengthening of the interactions between molecules.

When powders are introduced into the jelly marmalade recipe, the removal of sugar increases the product's nutritional value and shortens the time required for gel formation. Additionally, the high water-absorption properties of the powders improve the structural-mechanical characteristics of the jelly marmalade mass.

Moreover, for the samples with 50% and 75% powder, the spraying method for shaping the marmalade is recommended. This method ensures uniform structure and strength, simplifying the technological processes.

Overall, apple and carrot pomace-based powders can be successfully used as an alternative to sugar in jelly marmalade production. This not only enhances the product's quality but also opens up new possibilities for creating innovative and healthy food products.

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